

PROJECT LOGS:Yeast Growth on Fibrous Scaffolds”

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OBJECTIVE:grow yeast cells(*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*)

In a Agar based growth medium

And after 24h transfer it into a sterile tube with a nutritive liquid and observe the changements that will occur

MATERIALS:

-Scaffold: sterile gauze fiber

-Inoculum: diluted yeast

-Nutrient gel: 1g of agar + 5g of sugar + 100ml of water

-Observation: 900× zoom fonctionnelle microscope

PROCEDURE:

Step1: preparation of the nutrient gel

Step2: inoculation of the scaffold and the diluted yeast

Step3: incubation at room temperature for 24hours

MISTAKES

I did the same mistake three times it was simply putting agar and sugar after boiling water so I simply needed to put agar and sugar in water and after boil it
After this text I will usually do observation and write down what I see

T+7:At naked eye I see nothing new at 14:25 I will take a sample of the scaffold and document with a drawing what I see under the microscope

Without a colorant I couldn't properly see yeast cells I've only seen one that was attached to the scaffold with is in **brown** and the yeast cell in **red**
I suppose that I just need more material but also that some cells didn't divide and we're invisible

Transfer

For this step of the experiment the goal is that I grow more cells by transferring only the scaffold from gel to a nutritive water made out of warm water and sugar all of these into a sterile tube and will note personal observations

T+1

No visible change the yeast is in acclimation phase

T+4

No change it seems that the yeast is dead I will proceed to a microscopic analysis

After observing the sample I declare the yeast dead

T+6 (major update)

I did a mistake the cells aren't dead but they are colonizing the scaffold I analysed the water and forgot the scaffold

So there is what I saw in the microscope

With the conditions of 100× zoom without diaphragm and with blue glass

I suppose that the point between the fibers is a yeast cells who has been compressed
And the $\frac{1}{4}$ of circle is a forming yeast cell

T+21

After wanting to observe a sample under the microscope I realized that the water flowed out the tube the scaffold was still in the tube with a little bit of water in contact of it

I replaced the water by a new one and I decided to wait 28hours to let the yeast rest and multiply and see it under a microscope

These are the conditions I watched it under the microscope

×450

Middle diaphragm

Without colorant

After observation under the microscope under the conditions I told

I suppose that the red cell has this form because pressure was applied to it between the fibers

The green cell is perfect she has all the characteristics of a perfect yeast cell

For the blue cell I suppose that she is currently dividing more precisely in the first step and it is the only cell that is detached of the scaffold

Under naked eye the water is normal my hypothesis is that all the cells are on the scaffold except some but not a big quantity

REPORT OF THE EXPERIMENT

In the experiment I learned how to create a nutritive bridge and grow cells I also learned the perfect ratio for a perfect agar gel

In the second part I learned how to setup a microscope how to sterilize material and how to identify some cells and air bubbles

In general I learned a lot of useful skills like redaction of a scientific report

I declare the experiment a success

Source: Salim Eloualdrhi's Personal Lab book